

A Super-Homogenisation(SPH)-based Pin-wise Cross-Section (XS) Optimization Scheme for PARCS: Development, Verification, and First Application to a Small Modular Reactor (SMR)

Kanglong Zhang, Luigi Mercatali, Victor Hugo Sanchez-Espinoza

Hermann-von-Helmholtz-Platz 1, 76344 Eggenstein-Leopoldshafen, Germany

kanglong.zhang@kit.edu, luigi.mercatali@kit.edu, victor.sanchez@kit.edu

ABSTRACT

Based on the Super-Homogenisation (SPH) method, a Cross-Section (XS) optimization scheme was recently developed at the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT) for PARCS. The XS is pin-wise and homogenized from the Serpent heterogeneous solution. The first verification demonstrates that PARCS could produce more consistent pin-wise power fields using the SPH-optimized XS generated with Serpent2 than with the raw XS. Meanwhile, PARCS was extended at KIT to be able to perform pin-wise full-core simulations with the Nodal Expansion Method (NEM). PARCS along with this new function was applied to an academic testing mini core and the KIT SMR (KSMR, concept based on the SMART reactor) to perform a full-core pin-by-pin simulation using the XS optimized by the SPH-based system. The results demonstrate that the XS optimization can significantly improve the PARCS diffusion solver in predicting pin-conserving power field with Serpent results. Furthermore, the optimized pin-wise simulation gives better prediction in the core center area compared to the traditional assembly-wise solution with the Pin Power Reconstruction (PPR) method. Shortly, the SPH-assisted and functional-extended PARCS will be coupled to the subchannel code SubChanFlow (SCF) to perform full-core pin/subchannel level simulation in a multi-physics approach.

KEYWORDS: Super-Homogenisation(SPH), Cross-Section(XS), PARCS, Serpent, Pin-wise

1. INTRODUCTION

For nuclear safety analysis, sometimes it is necessary to accurately predict the pin power for local safety considerations. The typical diffusion or transport solvers are usually based on the Pin Power Reconstruction (PPR) methodology, which is a complementary feature of the standard nodal methodology. For the nodal method that is widely applied in diffusion or transport codes, a resolution is done at the level of the complete homogenized assembly. Then, the pin power is reconstructed using the group-wise form function obtained from a heterogeneous solution at pin-level. On one side this method has the advantage of fast running speed and predictable pin power, but on the other side it does not allow to model the local pin-wise Thermal-Hydraulic (TH) feedback and this poses a limitation for the pin-level multi-physics simulation which should be closer to reality.

As a consequence, pin-level resolved core simulations with actual condensed and homogenized pin-wise XSs are necessary. One drawback of this method is the long-running time. The other drawback is the homogenization error in the material properties, which could be significant. The validity of the diffusion

and SP3 equations is known to be weak in regions with high neutron absorption or high neutron leakages. To cope with this limitation, the Super-Homogenisation (SPH) homogenization method was proposed by Kavenoky in 1978 [1] to optimize the pin-wise homogenized Cross-Section (XS) for transport codes. After years of consistent effort by Hébert [2] [3] [4] [5], the SPH calculation algorithm can nowadays be considered mature and standardized [5]. The SPH method is based on the generation of homogenized XSs for transport codes based on the results of the heterogeneous solution for the transport code to preserve the reaction rates with the latter. In recent years, several efforts were made to improve the SPH performance e.g. the optimization of flux discontinuity between assemblies [6] and the variant PJFNK-SPH method (Preconditioned Jacobian-Free Newton–Krylov) [7] [8]. This method is continuously drawing the community’s attention and has been applied to various codes and conditions [9] [10] [11]. Recently, this method is also combined with multi-physics systems for more reliable simulations [12].

At Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), R&D activities are ongoing aiming to develop calculation schemes capable to analyze local safety parameters, in particular by coupling the PARCS [13] core neutronic code and sub-channel TH solvers at the pin level. Thus, as the pre-condition, PARCS needs to be able to perform simulation for an entire reactor core at pin-level, and with the SPH-optimized XSs. In this approach, the XSs are generated using the Serpent2 Monte Carlo code [14]. The main idea behind the SPH-based scheme is the optimization of the Serpent2 pin-wise XSs through the conservation of the neutron reaction rates of PARCS with those of Serpent2.

2. DESCRIPTION OF THE SPH-BASED OPTIMIZATION SYSTEM

This system applies an iterative technique to generate a set of so-called SPH factors to correct the XSs for each equivalence region and energy group of PARCS. For example, there would be 18 SPH factors if the model had 9 pins with 2 energy groups. Before explaining the working principles of the SPH system, it is worth spending some words on the motivations why SPH is necessary for pin-level XS optimization to be used by codes like PARCS. As shown in **Figure 1**, Serpent2 can produce various statics data and some of them e.g. the total reaction rate, total fission rate, total neutron flux, etc would be used to generate pin-level XSs which would be used by PARCS. Here we assume that Serpent is accurate and treat its result as the reference. Due to the difference in solvers, with the XS by Serpent2, the neutron flux predicted by PARCS should be different from Serpent2, thus leading to different neutron rates (including total reaction, fission, etc). Our goal is to use SPH to reduce this difference as much as possible.

Figure 1 – The motivations of the SPH development.

The SPH system uses an iteration technique whose working principles are explained in **Figure 2**. According to this scheme, at first, a Serpent2 run on a 2D reflected fuel assembly (FA) model is needed to produce the heterogeneous lattice reference solution (usually a Serpent2 run for each FA type is needed, which produces the pin-wise results). Then, the PARCS solver runs over a series of iterations (typically two iterations are enough) to tune its pin-by-pin predicted reaction rates to the reference ones of Serpent2. During the iteration,

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once a step is finished, the SPH factors for the next step are calculated using the current PARCS flux and the reference Serpent2 flux. Then the PARCS XSs for each region and energy group will be updated by multiplying those factors. Once the differences in neutron reaction rates between PARCS and Serpent2 satisfy the convergence criterion, then the iteration will end.

Figure 2 – The working principles of the SPH system demonstrate the iteration procedures.

All of the above principles are implemented based on Python scripts. This SPH-based optimization system is composed of multiple files.

3. PIN-WISE FUNCTIONAL EXTENSION FOR PARCS

The current version of PARCS used in KIT is V.331. It has two approaches for the generation of the pin-wise field:

- 1) Nodal solver + Pin Power Reconstruction (PPR). This approach runs fast and can predict pin power distributions through the reconstruction from form functions therefore this is not meant to be a real pin-level simulation.
- 2) Fine Mesh Finite Difference (FMFD) kernel. This is an SP3 solver and can run real pin-level simulations whereas the fuel rod pin is not explicitly defined (the definition is from rod -> assembly -> core). The “assembly” layer wrapping the fuel rods places additional obstacles to achieving pin-level TH feedback.

Since we want a real pin-level simulation and the explicitly-defined fuel rod to enable the pin-level TH feedback, neither of the above approaches works properly. Straightforwardly, we extend the capability of PARCS with the normal NEM or ANM nodal solvers instead of the FMFD kernel, for the benefits of the explicit pin definition feature. However, with the normal nodal solvers e.g. NEM or ANM, PARCS was found not able to process “big cases” e.g. 200x200 size problems.

Over a large number of trials, the faults were located in the input and output processing. They are kind of a “capacity” or “data traffic” problem. This limitation was successfully eliminated by modifying the PARCS source. Now, the KIT variant of PARCS V331 can process “big data” with normal nodal solvers. This paves the way for applying the SPH system to full core analysis.

4. VERIFICATION OF THE SPH-BASED OPTIMIZATION SYSTEM

The SPH-based methodology described in the previous Section has been verified using two different test cases, namely a 9 KONVOI-type FAs-based mini-core and the KIT Small Modular Reactor (KSMR).

4.1 Verification with a 3x3 mini core

The core consists of 9 German KONVOI-type assemblies in a 3x3 layout. The radial layout of the assemblies is given in **Figure 3**. For simplification, the axial height of the assemblies to be used in the mini-core is reduced to 1 cm.

Figure 3 – The generic radial layout of KONVOI-type fuel assembly (left, orange – normal fuel rod, yellow – boron or water rod, purple – control or water rod) and the simplified axial dimension to be used in the mini core (right).

Two types of assemblies are used to model the mini-core: a) all rods in; b) all rods out. The two assemblies are pre-simulated with the SPH system and the result of PARCS with the optimized pin-level XS was verified well agreeing with the Serpent2 solution, **Figure 4**. By applying the implemented SPH methodology, the maximum difference in the normalized power between PARCS and Serpent2 has been reduced from 0.45% (with raw XSs) to 0.02% (with optimized XSs).

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Figure 4 – Pin-level simulations in the assemblies (top – all rods out, bottom – all rods in) (left – Serpent2 solution, middle – the difference between PARCS and Serpent with the raw XS, right – the difference between PARCS and Serpent with the SPH-optimized XS).

Based on the assembly simulations, the mini-core was modeled consisting of 9 such assemblies in a 3x3 layout. The surrounding 8 assemblies have all rods out (the top case in **Figure 4**), and the central assembly has all rods in (the bottom case in **Figure 4**). The result of the first case is given in **Figure 5**. There, the normalized power distribution of Serpent2 is the reference. Three different simulations have been performed with PARCS: a) regular assembly level with the PPR; b) pin level with the raw XS; c) pin level with the SPH-optimized XSs. As far as the eight external FAs, from **Figure 5** one can observe that the differences between the three calculations are not significant. However, for the central FA, the PARCS calculation without SPH correction was found to produce a rather big difference. PARCS with traditional solution has a small difference in this area, however, the difference at the boundaries (especially the four corners) is still significant. As the best solution, PARCS with SPH produces lower differences not only in the central assembly but also at its boundaries/corners.

Figure 5 - The normalized power distributions and differences between PARCS and Serpent2 for the mini core (leftmost – Serpent2 solution, middle left - the difference between PARCS and Serpent2 with assembly-level simulation and PPR, middle right - the difference between PARCS and Serpent2 with the raw XSs, rightmost – the difference between PARCS and Serpent2 with the SPH-optimized XSs).

4.2 Verification with the KSMR core

The radial and axial cross-sections of the KSMR core and control rod configuration are displayed in **Figure 6** and **Figure 7**. The core has 57 fuel assemblies in 6 types and 2 poison types [15]. The reflectors shown in the picture are dummy assemblies that are exactly filled with water. The control rods are of six different types and are composed of three different neutron absorbers.

Figure 6 - The radial and axial layout of the fuel assemblies of the KSMR core.

Figure 7 - The radial and axial layout of the control rods of the KSMR core (AIC – AgInCd, SS – stainless Steel, B4C – Boron Carbide).

The normalized power distributions are given in **Figure 8**. We can observe that the Pin-on-SPH result is similar to Ass-PPR while Pin-no-SPH differs from the other two (the hot part is hotter and the cold part is colder).

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Figure 8 - The normalized power distributions predicted by PARCS for KSMR (left – assembly-level + PPR, middle – pin-level raw XS, right – pin-level SPH-optimized XS).

Figure 9 displays the normalized power difference between the three fields in **Figure 8** and the result of Serpent2. For better illustration, the maximum value of the error bar is set to 6%. By comparing the three differences' figures, it is evident that the PARCS simulation with raw XSs produces the most significant difference which indicates that, without optimization, the XSs are not applicable for pin-wise simulation of PARCS. The pin-wise simulation of PARCS with SPH-optimized XSs produces a similar low difference as the assembly-wise simulation with PPR. Nevertheless, the difference is still obvious. That is, the former produces a lower difference in the central area while has a larger difference at the boundaries.

Figure 9 - The axially-averaged normalized power differences between PARCS and Serpent for KSMR (left – assembly-level + PPR, middle – pin-level raw XS, right – pin-level SPH-optimized XS).

The 3D difference distributions of the three simulations are plotted in **Figure 10**. One can observe that the traditional nodal solution with PPR gives good predictions in the core central region as well as in the boundary regions. However, the fields at the top and bottom of the core active region are not well predicted. Furthermore, obvious discontinuities could be observed because this is not a real pin-level simulation, and some hypotheses are applied. With the pin-level XS, we can run a real pin-level simulation with PARCS. However, the differences are unacceptable either in the central region or the boundary region. Thus it is not practical for any pin-level safety analysis. Fortunately, the SPH-optimized XS brings the good news by reducing the central difference markedly. The power distributes smoothly thanks to its real pin-level nature.

Figure 10 - The 3D spatial normalized power differences between PARCS and Serpent for KSMR (left – assembly-level + PPR, middle – pin-level raw XS, right – pin-level SPH-optimized XS).

An encouraging finding compared to the traditional solution is that the pin-level simulation with the optimized XSs performs better in the regions that are adjacent to the top and bottom reflectors. However, the result is poor in the regions that are adjacent to the radial reflectors. This might be due to the poor modeling of the radial reflector (in pin-level) that has been done in Serpent and the resulting not-well XS of those reflectors. Another reason could be that the reflector is modeled by pure water, which is not a real representation of the actual reflector conditions. Further study is necessary to figure out this problem.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, an SPH-based methodology recently developed at KIT aiming to optimize the homogenized pin-wise XSs produced by Serpent2 for the PARCS code has been presented. Moreover, a pin-wise simulation functional extension to PARCS is briefly discussed as well for the sake of full core simulation. The methodology has been verified against two different test cases, namely a nine CONVOI-type FAs mini-core and the 57 FAs KSMR (KIT Small Modular Reactor). The results indicate that the SPH-based system can significantly improve the pin-level power prediction of PARCS with the optimized pin-level XSs. This makes the pin-level TH feedback possible to better predict the local safety parameters in the reactor core.

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REFERENCES

- [1] A. Kavenoky, "The SPH homogenization method," in *Homogenization methods in reactor physics*, Lugano, Switzerland, 13-15, 11, 1978.
- [2] A. Hébert and A. Kavenoky, "Development of the SPH homogenization method," in *International topical meeting on advances in mathematical methods for nuclear engineering problems*, Munich, Germany, 1981.
- [3] A. Hébert and P. Benoist, "A Consistent Technique for the Global Homogenization of a Pressurized Water Reactor Assembly," *Nuclear Science and Engineering*, vol. 109, no. 4, pp. 360-372, 1991.

- [4] A. Hébert, "A Consistent Technique for the Pin-by-Pin Homogenization of a Pressurized Water Reactor Assembly," *Nuclear Science and Engineering*, vol. 113, no. 3, pp. 227-238, 1993.
- [5] A. Hébert and G. Mathonnière, "Development of a Third-Generation Superhomogénéisation Method for the Homogenization of a Pressurized Water Reactor Assembly," *Nuclear Science and Engineering*, vol. 115, no. 2, pp. 129-141, 1993.
- [6] A. YAMAMOTO, M. TATSUMI, Y. KITAMURA and Y. YAMANE, "Improvement of the SPH Method for Pin-by-Pin Core Calculations," *Journal of NUCLEAR SCIENCE and TECHNOLOGY*, vol. 41, no. 12, pp. 1155-1165, 2004.
- [7] J. Ortensi, Y. Wang, A. Laurier, S. Schunert, A. Hébert and M. DeHart, "A Newton solution for the Superhomogenization method: The PJFNK-SPH," *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, vol. 111, pp. 579-594, 2018.
- [8] V. Labouré, Y. Wang, J. Ortensi, S. Schunert, F. Gleicher, M. DeHart and R. Martineau, "Hybrid super homogenization and discontinuity factor method for continuous finite element diffusion," *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, vol. 128, no. 2019, pp. 443-454, 2019.
- [9] U. Grundmann and S. Mittag, "Super-homogenisation factors in pinwise calculations by the reactor dynamics code DYN3D," *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, vol. 38, pp. 2111-2119, 2011.
- [10] S. S. H. Hiruta, "Super-Homogenization-Corrected Cross-Section Generation for High-Temperature Reactors," Idaho National Laboratory, Idaho, 2017.
- [11] Y. Yuan, G. Liu and X. Huo, "Implementation and Comparison of Super Homogenization Method Based on Monte Carlo and Deterministic Codes," in *2022 29th International Conference on Nuclear Engineering*, Virtual, Online, 2022.
- [12] Z. Xiangyue, L. Xiaojing, X. Chai, H. Hui, Z. Bin and Z. Tengfei, *Multi-Physics Coupled Simulation of Small Mobile Nuclear Reactor with Finite Element-Based Models*, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4360932>, 2023.
- [13] Y. Xu and V. Seker, "PARCS v3.0 U.S. NRC Core Neutronics Simulator," U.S. NRC, Rockville, Md, 2012.
- [14] J. Leppänen, M. Pusa, T. Viitanen, V. Valtavirta and T. Kaltiaisenaho, "The Serpent Monte Carlo code: Status, development and applications in 2013," *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, vol. 82, pp. 142-150, 2013.
- [15] Y. Alzaben and R. S. V.H. Sanchez-Espinoza, "Core nertronics and safety characteristics of a boron-free core for Small Modular Reactors," *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, vol. 132, pp. 70-81, 2019.